

The Research Data Culture Conversation

Response to ARDC

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Preface

Research intensive universities are working together to articulate the nature of a sustainable and effective research data culture, under the banner of the Research Data Culture Conversation (RDCC). A culture change is needed, around the practice of data management, at an all-of-university and all-of-research sector scale.

The Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) is a transformational initiative that enables Australian research community and industry access to nationally significant, leading edge data intensive eInfrastructure, platforms, skills and collections of high-quality data. It recognises that institutions and research organisations play a vital role in any national data framework and that an alignment of institutional and national infrastructure arrangements can drive better data management practices and outcomes.

Following some discussion around the way in which institutional and national data infrastructure investments might add value to each other, the ARDC posed the following general questions:

1. How should national and institutional data collections infrastructure integrate into a more coherent national data system?
2. How to best articulate the role of an institution in a national data commons and the institutions' expectations vis a vis the ARDC)?
3. What ongoing arrangements/structures might be required for that purpose?
4. How investments in FAIR (and other national priorities) be aligned with investment in institutional priorities such as GDPR, sensitive data, disposal and capacities at large.

The ARDC also invited feedback on two strategic concepts it had expressed support for:

1. Distributed national collections; and
2. A national FAIR data safety net.

See the appendix for the full text from the ARDC.

The paper provides a summary of the progress of the RDCC (Section 2), identifies emerging themes and an initial set of activities that could progress those themes (sections 3 and 4) and concludes by relating those themes and activities to the questions posed (section 5).

This project is supported by the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC). The ARDC is enabled by NCRIS.

1 Executive Summary

This report follows on from the companion RDCC paper - Summary of the Challenge.

We are in an era where digitisation and information assurance encompasses all research domains. The Research Data Culture Conversation (RDCC) has canvassed the complexities of university hosted research data. It is a conversation between those building solutions today, those who look to adopt a solution and those that can facilitate change in research practice.

Put simply, we must amass, develop and promulgate best practices to empower more effective and affordable data management at an all-of-university scale.

The ARDC invited the RDCC to provide advice on how research data practice improvements made within institutions could relate to national collections and national initiatives. The goal is for the Universities and the ARDC to coordinate towards whole-of-sector benefits.

The proposition is that RDMP-2.0 is an integration of university functions rather than an orthogonal plan. Smart Decision Making encompasses the processes and standards that allows information about data collected over its life cycles to trigger actions when data passes through a transition in its life cycles. Significant challenges exist, including:

- The discipline specific variability in the nature of life cycle events and their appropriate actions;
- The best use of automation in the detection of events and the actioning of responses; and
- Interacting with internal and external systems to achieve optimal tiering and replication outcomes.

However, once achieved within individual universities, and then if harmonised across universities, it would also be the case that:

- A FAIR Data safety net would exist and federated collections could be reliably and readily discoverable and constructed on data already being held within institutional systems;
- The value of data could be more easily balanced against the cost of storage; and more broadly
- Governmental policy goals relating to research data would be more easily met.

2 Research Data Culture Conversation

The emerging and encompassing transformation being sought through the RDCC requires increased coordination of research data management at an all-of-university scale.

The journey of the RDCC leads to the following observations:

- Data growth in research is now so rapid it threatens a budget shift across a university which cannot be sustained into the future - something about data needs to change;
- The ever increasing expansion of data holdings is driven by research opportunities;
- Data is a new asset class requiring new investment;
- The existing national data conversation is well developed in Preservation, Sharing and Re-use
- The national conversation on Resourcing, Sensitivity and End-of-Life needs strengthening;
- Research Data Management Plans must inform decision making and must deliver the productivity gains needed as data grows; and
- Institutions, which are a primary location where data ambitions and obligations meet budgets, need nationally-coherent discipline-sensitive responses to be defined

It is important that the development of a research data management process addresses these observations. University-wide and broader sector-wide benefits will only arise when all these observations are appropriately addressed.

Summary Goals:

We envisage a digital environment where automation is informed by the development, adoption and deployment of an RDMP-2.0 standard, which is researcher-led and community-driven.

We seek a perpetual and robust way to measure and inform best practice, through metadata-driven and machine-actioned management practices which capture the context of data sufficiently well to support most life-cycle decisions to be made about those data.

The intention is as follows.

- That the right people have access to the right data for the right amount of time.
- The cost of making decisions about data and data life cycles is reduced as is the human effort required in data curation.
- A cultural change occurs so that researchers can articulate the kind of data that have end-of-life events and so that institutions can implement end-of-life events.
- A resource aware practice develops so that retained data migrates towards lower cost and increasingly compliant retention solutions.

A Smart Decision Making (RDMP-2.0 based) process is envisaged, whereby research data management would transition from the current plan based aa(waterfall) approach to a continuous improvement-based approach.

The Smart Decision Making (SDM) process would:

- Translate best practice improvements arising in institutions into national practice by coordinating aligned activities;

- Realise FAIR principles through the harmonisation of metadata and by improving the coherence of systems supporting data;
- Improve efficiency and compliance within the core institutional support “pillars” (archives, data privacy, eResearch, ethics, IT, library, records, the research office and security):
 - By leveraging common metadata to automate better data management decisions as data progresses through its life cycles; and
 - By better relating cost to benefit

The RDCC paper - “Summary of the Challenge” sets out broad development themes, which are summarised below.

1) Research data practice

Improvement is dependent on the implementation of systems/processes in institutions and between institutions. This is very dependent on institutional and all pillars involvement. The showbag activity started by the RDCC is helpful to this.

- Dimensioning and then measuring current state
- Implementation of information capture around data
- Architecting a data migration framework (that meets policy and access realities)

2) Research data purpose

Improvement is dependent on the knowledge and capabilities of researchers. We need to define more effective life cycle concepts and community agreements around them. This is work that needs to be carried forward with the participation of researchers and domain specific data investments.

- Articulation of ‘normal practice’ in different data life cycles
- Maturing of Smart Decision Making in research data management

3) Research data investment

Improvement is dependent on the perceived value of research data. We need to understand the measures and decisions required in assigning value, clarify the goals of research data management with respect to the value and cost of data, and cross-inform and connect 1, and 2.

- Development of RDMP-2.0

3 Opportunity

The RDCC themes are foundational and support a very broad set of ambitions. For example an SDM process would improve research integrity and deliver more certain access to data underpinning published research, support university held prestige collections, the flow of data into science agency collections and support the data life cycles associated with data from all of the NCRIS capabilities.

The successful realisation of SDM would also mean that retention or disposal of an increasingly higher proportion of data would be properly actioned and the amount of data that could be retained would be increased with the automatic migration of data towards lower cost infrastructures.

Combined these significantly enhance the ability to achieve the outcomes nominated by the ARDC.

An SDM process could also retain data identified as part of a collection and provide information to a discovery and access system for such collections. A collection could be at a University or federated across many universities. If the data in the collection would have been retained, the cost is negligible. If additional data is retained because of the collection’s retention policy, the additional data would be known and the incremental cost of the federated collection negotiated between the collection’s supporters.

While the benefits of the FAIR principles appear at the system level, they are not necessarily prioritised by researchers doing research. Therefore the implementation of any new processes will need to consider the best approach to ‘blockers’ that could easily arise around researcher interest in RDMP-2.0. These include:

- the lack of capable and easy-to-use tools and services;
- the creation of extra work with no clear (immediate) benefits;
- the possible shortfall in facilitation and support from Universities to researchers; and
- that the competitive nature of research activities is real (i.e. data is a key resource to researchers to which they seek access control).

4 Next Steps

The developments set out here will take some considerable time to achieve. They would involve trialling and deploying the technology and the business processes around them. The harmonisation and alignment of RDMP-2.0 across the number of participants envisaged, will take many years. Before making that commitment, an evaluation phase could verify the concepts and approaches envisaged.

The aim of an evaluation phase could be to produce:

- Confidence that progress can be made;
- A high level project plan for a set of activities extending to 2025;
- A governance structure for those activities;
- Expressions of commitment from participants; and
- A plan for execution on a timeline appropriate to funding support available.

The engagement of the ARDC would materially improve the prospect of developing an RDMP-2.0.

5 Responses to Questions

General Questions

- A. How can national and institutional data collections infrastructure integrate into a more coherent national data system?
- B. What role should institutions have in a national data commons and what role does a national data common play for institutions?
- C. What ongoing arrangements/structures might be required for mutual value adding?
- D. How can investments in FAIR be aligned with institutional priorities such as GDPR, sensitive data, disposal and capacities at large?

In response:

- A. A national data system is an emergent outcome of the behaviour of its components. While the RDCC is an important stepping stone towards its realisation, a national data system emerges from the implementation of many separate components. The cohesion required is technical, involving standards and common interfaces, but more importantly social. The social infrastructure required is based around a commonality of process and culture. The endeavour put forward in this paper directly advances that ambition.
- B. Through the RDMP-2.0 and the implementation of Smart Decision Making solutions, institutions will develop the underlying content management capability needed by national collections. In addition, the pathways from laboratory data to reference collections would be codified and supported. This would be a direct contribution to an emerging Data Commons. Functionality including discovery, search and access interfaces could be provided as part of the data commons investment.
- C. A national and internationally consistent standards process for RDMP-2.0 would be necessary. This would include the definition of APIs and the accreditation of implementations. A means to cover the long term retention cost of data prioritised as a national collection would need to be resolved.
- D. The understanding required is yet to be developed. The strategy above involves strong engagement with disciplines in order to gain the researcher and research support input that will be required. An enduring national discipline engagement process needs to be established and energised.

Distributed National Collections

ARDC specific question : As part of an open co-design process ARDC seeks input from institutional infrastructure and data governance providers / capabilities on whether this model would align with institutional ambitions and if so how it best can be aligned.

The RDCC activity and the work plan outlined above does support the model put forward by the ARDC. The governance of discipline data is set forward as a challenge to be resolved.

National FAIR Safety Net

ARDC specific question : As part of an open co-design process ARDC seeks input from institutional infrastructure & data governance providers / capabilities on a) ARDC's preliminary assumptions of the role of institutions in establishing research discipline led national commons, and b) the role ARDC can play in promoting collaboration, coordination, and coherence.

The RDCC has focussed on productivity of services supporting discipline defined life cycle events and has not specifically considered the creation of a national data commons. The nature of a national cooperative programme for a national commons suggests a national governance and support organisation which is outside the scope of the current challenges facing Universities.

The RDCC assumption is that disciplines may have different life cycles and those differences need specific responses, whereas the notion of a single national data commons leads to sentiments as expressed in the ARDC text referring to common aspects of life cycle across disciplines.

The work plan leads to mechanisms that would provide certainty of data in its agreed lifecycles in a national data commons.

5 Appendix - Full Text of Request from ARDC

The RDCG is an informal volunteer group of institutional infrastructure & data governance providers / capabilities currently comprised of participants from seven universities. It is chaired by Steve Quenette of Monash University, has Rhys Francis as an independent coordinator, and is supported by an organisational steering committee includes Steve, Luc Betbeder-Matibet of the University of NSW, Steve Giugni of the University of Melbourne, and Andrew Janke of Sydney University. The RDCG's premise is as follows:

- A. Due to the continuing exponential growth in data creation and use, institutions will increasingly coordinate large-scale infrastructure to support research data; and
- B. The efficient use of such infrastructure requires information, and the recognition of constraints, that must involve researchers.
- C. Additional challenges then arise, because:
- D. Research data lifecycles relate to activities traditionally owned by DVCsR, library, records, archive and IT and more recently eResearch activities; and
- E. Efficiencies, scalability, quality improvements and opportunities for strategic prioritisation require a coordination of a researcher's data through these pillars.

ARDC

The ARDC recognises that institutions and research organisations play a vital role in any national data framework. An alignment of institutional and national infrastructure arrangements can drive better data management practices and outcomes. The ARDC is seeking input from the sector on the alignment that would best assist progress with:

3. Distributed national collections; and
4. A national FAIR data safety net.

ARDC questions:

5. How should national and institutional data collections infrastructure integrate into a more coherent national data system?
6. How to best articulate the role of an institution in a national data commons and the institutions' expectations vis a vis the ARDC)?
7. What ongoing arrangements/structures might be required for that purpose?
8. How investments in FAIR (and other national priorities) be aligned with investment in institutional priorities such as GDPR, sensitive data, disposal and capacities at large.

Distributed national collections.

Many disciplines and subdisciplines do not (and may never have) national collections which are directly or wholly supported by national research infrastructure. For example, not all areas of marine science are covered by IMOS; not all areas of earth science are covered by AuScope; large areas of HASS are not covered by any formal national body; typically health studies data remain aligned with various faculties, institutes, hospitals, or state governments.

On the institutional side, Universities have the short and long term responsibilities for data produced by their researchers. These university-based researchers represent a substantive cohort of users of national research infrastructure. The universities also host a significant amount of the actual data-generating infrastructure, and the subsequently valuable data outputs. When institutional data systems are implemented solely driven by institutional concerns the research domains' data becomes fragmented across the country, and counter-intuitive to the establishment of a commons.

There are incentives therefore for both the disciplines and the institutions to establish what we are describing here as "Distributed National Collections".

In order to motivate universities, national research infrastructure and research domains to create national-scale collections leveraging the natural motivation for institutions to invest in institutionally governed resources, ARDC proposes to:

1. Resource the formalisation of discipline-specific (community) good practice for:
 - a. particular data types (e.g. good practice data quality for linguistics fieldwork)
 - b. access and governance (e.g. technical and social expectations of linguistics fieldworkers)
2. Catalyse participation in a distributed national collection from leading research organisations in that field (eg leading linguistics institutions implementing their own nodes of national distributed fieldwork collection)

The approach aims to create transformative distributed national collections that by gluing to orthogonal motivations: (a) are sustained by long-lived institutions, and (b) are energised by national research communities.

Specifically this accelerates the technical capability of the disciplines to both scalably and sustainably exchange information from universities into a commons, by engaging, leveraging and contributing to university data transformations.

ARDC specific question : As part of an open co-design process ARDC seeks input from institutional infrastructure and data governance providers / capabilities on whether this model would align with institutional ambitions and if so how it best can be aligned.

National FAIR safety net - a data governance capability

An important component of a national data system is developing and supporting a "commons approach" to the management of data by projects hosted and managed by the institutions and research organisations.

Within institutions, a broad range of data arrangements (data policy, guidelines, infrastructure, support mechanisms) have developed and been implemented to improve the efficiency, integrity, and impact of research projects. Across the institutions these arrangements have resulted in a wide variety of selection, appraisal, retention, and deletion schedules. Some of this is the result of different state legislation but is mostly an outcome of lack of coordination and lack of agreement on common standards and principles.

There is an opportunity to improve alignment and coordination across the institutions to agree on common data lifecycle principles aligned to FAIR. The goal is to develop a data governance capability leading to a National FAIR data standards which would enable the establishment of a National FAIR “safety net” for important data hosted within the institutions.

These data may include: various software packages, algorithms, models and samples that underpin ongoing Australian research. These data would be systematically managed and be made available by the institutions as appropriate

ARDC sees the benefit of a common approach to data management.

It is assumed that many of these data are part of the institutional and not national infrastructure, ARDC proposes to contribute to the coherence and coordination of these institutional data arrangements by:

- helping to identify, share and systematise good practice.
- Incentivise adoption of best practices at scale
- facilitate cross-institutional collaboration

Specifically this accelerates research disciplines data governance capability to scalably / sustainably exchange information from universities into a commons, by engaging, leveraging and contributing to university data transformations.

ARDC specific question : As part of an open co-design process ARDC seeks input from institutional infrastructure & data governance providers / capabilities on a) ARDC’s preliminary assumptions of the role of institutions in establishing research discipline led national commons, and b) the role ARDC can play in promoting collaboration, coordination, and coherence.